

CAUSAL BEHAVIOUR OF ISOTROPICALLY COLLAPSED PRIMORDIAL GAS AND ITS CONSEQUENCES ON LIGHT PASSAGE

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ABSTRACT. We develop a mathematical formalism able of describing SSS spacetime null hypersurfaces to study the causal behaviour of isotropically collapsed gas and its consequences on the passage of light of cosmological origin. We assume that the perfect spherical gas is described by the Oppenheimer-Volkoff (O-V) metric and the external cosmological spacetime is the Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker (FLRW) solution to Einstein's Field Equations (E.F.E.). The closed-flux formalism is a suitable manner to handle light bundles and it optimizes lensing numerical calculations. The metrical junction is provided by the Israel-Darmois conditions which ultimately describes a thin shell on the boundary between the SSS and FLRW spacetimes. It is found that the background radiation path is perturbed by the passage inside the SSS gas and its redshift differs from the classical cosmological prediction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Theory of Structure Formation is based on Jeans Theory, or its relativistic analogues, which describes the gravitational collapse originated from fluctuations inside of the homogeneous and isotropic gas. These fluctuations seem to be able to explain the formation of cosmological structures on the large scales: galaxy clusters, dark matter halos etc.. The phenomenon of non-isotropic/homogeneous collapse implies a direct violation of the Cosmological Principle on the structure scales, the right choice of spacetime metric in these circumstances must then consider both scenarios: an internal collapsed and dense region with an external evolving and symmetric universe. There has been various attempts within the framework of general relativity, starting from Lifshitz (1946) and the works of Silk (1967,1968), Doroshkevich (1967), Peebles and Yu (1970), Field (1971), Weinberg (1971) and Chibisov (1972) developed a mathematical description with the purpose of deriving structure formation and the theory of galaxy formation in particular. Modern cosmology is based on the fact that galaxies were formed as a result of longitudinal adiabatic perturbation in the primordial fluid. The various studies on the Cosmic Microwave Background radiation (CMB) have shown that the original matter-energy distribution was much more isotropic and homogeneous in accordance with the Cosmological Principle. Modern theories must reconcile the early symmetric and homogeneous distribution with the present highly inhomogeneous and diverse universe. An important experimental test for these theories is the study of temperature fluctuations in the CMB, these could be then be the cause of the gravitational instabilities that lead to anisotropic collapse and structure formation eventually. Due to the fact that in the smallest scales of collapse our universe cannot be described by the FLRW metric, the passage of light and its energy should have been perturbed with respect to the linear evolution in the former metric. These perturbations could serve as a more scrupulous verification or falsification of our theories and would break the symmetries of the radiative components of the primordial fluid. Following the process illustrated from Zel'dovich and Barenblatt (1958) it can be derived that a spherical perturbation in which the density ρ_p differs from the external ρ evolves in the same way as the universe model. Starting from a $\rho_p > \rho$ case of a homogeneous and isotropic sphere, the final destiny of this partition of the universe can be quite diverse: classical singular solution diverging into a black hole, fragmentation of the initial cloud into smaller ones following the Jeans's process, dark matter halos formation for example. If one supposes that the initial gravitational collapse

will eventually stop as result of internal pressure of the original cloud or its fragmentation, then it should constitute a hydrostatic equilibrium. This static state is then well described by a Static Spherically Symmetric perfect fluid in hydrostatical equilibrium with the internal gravitational pull if the heat-stress and viscosity effects can be neglected, hence it can be uniquely delineated by its density ρ and pressure p . The metric suitable for such a energy-momentum characterization is the Oppenheimer-Volkoff (1939) solution to E.F.E., originally used from the authors to describe relativistic effects of neutron stellar cores.

1.1. Preliminaries. We will look at the problem of evolving matter and energy fields in a static metric, this is the case for O-V as we will see in the next section. In this static environment, to completely characterize causality it's useful to define some mathematical objects living in a generic manifold M and considering an achronal subset $S \subset M$, where achronal means that there are no two points in S connected by a timelike curve.

- (1) **Causal Curve:** $\gamma : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow M$ a time-like or null path in spacetime.
- (2) **Causal Future (Past)** $J^\pm(S)$ the set of points $p \in M$ which can be reached following a future (past)-directed γ from a subset $S \subset M$.
- (3) **Future (Past) Domain of Dependence** $D^\pm(S)$ the set of points $p \in M$ such that every inextendible causal curve through p must intersect S , formally $D^\pm(S) = \{p \in M \mid \exists t : \gamma(t) = p \implies \exists t_0 : \gamma(t_0) \in S\}$ with t is the future (past).
- (4) We will call the boundary of the $D^\pm(S)$ **Future (Past) Cauchy Horizon** $H^\pm(S)$.

Under the conditions that apply to O-V, there could be an important additional type of null-hypersurface which is the Event Horizon (EH), this is the case of a system well predicted by O-V metric with an internal region described by the Schwarzschild metric. In this scenario equations of motion and the metric components themselves become degenerate at the horizon for the asymptotic flat coordinates. Since we are interested at finding a global description of spacetime and dynamics, it's fundamental to prove that this conjunction obeys to the Darmois-Israel junction rules. To study causality and give an explicit form of these causal objects listed, it's necessary to derive the equations of motion in the metric to establish γ .

2. OPPENHEIMER-VOLKOFF METRIC AND TOV EQUATION

The general positively defined SSS metric can be written in the form:

$$(2.1) \quad ds^2 = -e^{2\alpha(r)} dt^2 + e^{2\beta(r)} dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2$$

By imposing the Einstein equations for non-vacuum solutions ($T_{\mu\nu} \neq 0$), we get four equations:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{tt} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{tt} &= \frac{1}{r^2} e^{2(\alpha-\beta)} (2r \partial_r \beta - 1 + e^{2\beta}) \\ R_{rr} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{rr} &= \frac{1}{r^2} (2r \partial_r \alpha + 1 - e^{2\beta}) \\ R_{\theta\theta} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\theta\theta} &= r^2 e^{-2\beta} (\partial_r^2 \alpha + (\partial_r \alpha)^2 - \partial_r \alpha \partial_r \beta + \frac{1}{r} (\partial_r \alpha - \partial_r \beta)) \\ R_{\phi\phi} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\phi\phi} &= \sin^2(\theta) G_{\theta\theta} \end{aligned}$$

To determine the coefficients α, β , we impose the perfect fluid condition on the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$.

$$(2.2) \quad T_{\mu\nu} = (\rho + p) U_\mu U_\nu + p g_{\mu\nu}$$

This fluid uniquely characterizes the metric, we demand its staticness by:

$$U_\mu = (e^\alpha, 0, 0, 0)$$

The solutions of this set of equations implies:

$$(2.3) \quad \begin{cases} e^{2\beta} = \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right]^{-1} \\ \frac{d\alpha}{dr} = \frac{m(r) + 4\pi r^3 p}{r(r - 2m(r))} \end{cases}$$

Subsequently from the continuity equation $\nabla_\mu T^{\mu\nu} = 0$ we have:

$$(2.4) \quad (p + \rho) \frac{d\alpha}{dr} = -\frac{dp}{dr}$$

From the last identities we finally get the Tolman-Oppenheimer-Volkoff equilibrium equation.

$$(2.5) \quad \frac{dp}{dr} = -\frac{(\rho + p)[m(r) + 4\pi r^3 p]}{r[r - 2m(r)]}$$

3. SYMMETRIES AND EQUATIONS OF MOTION

We would like to find a solution to the equation of motion in the case of null geodesics, in this way we can describe all the possible γ curves that define the causality of our manifold.

$$(3.1) \quad \frac{d^2 x^\mu}{d\lambda^2} + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^\mu \frac{dx^\alpha}{d\lambda} \frac{dx^\beta}{d\lambda} = 0$$

With λ the affine parameter to the null geodesic.

These are second order non-linear differential equations, it will prove useful to use Killing's identities associated with the symmetries of the theory to evaluate them. We start from the Killing equation

$$(3.2) \quad \nabla_{(\mu} K_{\nu)} = 0$$

There are two types of this fields in the O-V metric:

- (1) Time: $T^\mu = (1, 0, 0, 0)^T$.
- (2) Rotational(ϕ): $\Phi^\mu = (0, 0, 0, 1)^T$.

Applying separately the Killing identity $K_\mu u^\mu = K_\mu \frac{dx^\mu}{d\lambda} = C$, where K^μ stands for the generic Killing field provides us with a set of first order differential equations. From the SS of the metric there is also a conservation of total angular momentum.

$$(3.3) \quad \begin{cases} \dot{t} = E e^{-2\alpha(r)} \\ \dot{\theta}^2 = \frac{L^2}{r^4} - \frac{L_z^2}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)} \\ \dot{\phi} = \frac{L_z}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \end{cases}$$

While the physical meaning of the last two constants is straightforward, they correspond to the angular momentum contributions (z-axis, polar). The meaning of the first one should be investigated further, recalling the definition of the fourmomentum of a light particle we get:

$$(3.4) \quad p^\mu = \hbar k^\mu$$

Where, the wave fourvector $k^\mu = (\omega, \omega \vec{n})^T$. From the theory we can redefine the affine parameter $\lambda \rightarrow a\lambda + b$ while referring to the same curve (a, b constants). Knowing this fact, we can finally write $u^\mu = k^\mu$ which implies $\omega = E e^{2\alpha(r)} \xrightarrow{r \rightarrow +\infty} E$, it's clear now that E is the energy of the wave packet at infinity.

We conclude this section finding the last eq. of motion (r) from the null condition:

$$(3.5) \quad ds^2 = 0 \implies g_{\mu\nu} \frac{dx^\mu}{d\lambda} \frac{dx^\nu}{d\lambda} = 0$$

Using equations [3.3] in the general frame, we finally get:

$$(3.6) \quad \dot{r}^2 = E^2 \left(1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right) \left[e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \frac{L^2}{E^2 r^2}\right]$$

4. CAUSALLY CONNECTED SPACE

A globally causally connected spacetime M is defined by the fact that taken every two space points, at least one timelike geodesic connects them. This is the case for the Oppenheimer-Volkoff excluding the degeneracy portions of the manifold.

To see why we first have to talk about the properties of such a manifold:

- (1) It is endowed with only one metric $g_{\mu\nu}$ with asymptotic Minkowskian coordinates.
- (2) It is devoid of EHs.

The first property is assumed by hypothesis (the lack of degeneracies), the second one is to be proven. The EH is not a local phenomenon in spacetime, its presence (or lack there of) is clearly manifested in the case of SSS metrics. We can show that the O-V spacetime is devoid of EH by constructing a coordinate foliation able to find eventual trapped areas of the manifold M . Starting from the Killing vector T^μ , we can make sense of a coordinate system where (r, θ, ϕ) coordinates asymptotically describe spacelike hypersurfaces of $t = \text{constant}$.

The foliation is described by the asymptotically timelike $r = \text{constant}$ hypersurfaces, by the rotational symmetry it's known that this will have topology $\Sigma_r : \mathbb{S}^2 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ under the right choice of spherical coordinates. We can now study all the spacetime M by its submanifold Σ_r by varying r . From our initial consideration we know that $\lim_{r \rightarrow +\infty} \Sigma_r$ is timelike. An event horizon in this scheme will be found if and only if Σ_r becomes a null hypersurface for some value of r . To calculate the Lorentzian norm of the normal vector $\partial_\mu r$ we use the simple expression:

$$(4.1) \quad g^{\mu\nu}(\partial_\mu r)(\partial_\nu r) = g^{rr}$$

The EH is found when $g^{rr} = 0$, and in our case with the O-V metric, this is the case when:

$$(4.2) \quad g^{rr} = 1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r} = 0 \implies r = 2m(r)$$

Which is the Schwarzschild condition that we excluded in point (1) of this discussion.

This method is based on the fact that O-V spacetime is asymptotically flat, for this kind of spaces there is another way to characterize EH. In these conditions, the event horizons correspond to the Time Killing Horizon. We should then ask when does the T^μ field vanish in norm.

$$(4.3) \quad g_{\mu\nu}T^\mu T^\nu = g_{tt} = -e^{2\alpha(r)} = 0 \implies \alpha(r) \rightarrow -\infty$$

With these two independent method we can finally say that this "pure" O-V solution is devoid of EHs.

To finally prove that this pure Oppenheimer-Volkoff spacetime is causally connected we must show the following:

$$(4.4) \quad \mathfrak{Sp}(D^\pm(S)) = \mathfrak{Sp}(M)$$

For any arbitrary S .

With \mathfrak{Sp} we intend the space component of the set, in a formal way we can write it as the canonical projection from spacetime to three dimensional space.

$$(4.5) \quad \pi : M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3 \mid \pi(x^\mu) = x^i \quad \forall x^\mu \in M, g_{ii} > 0$$

This condition originates from the isometry through time. In this way every possible causal curve will always connect two arbitrarily chosen points. Equation [4.4] also implies that the border of the $D^\pm(S)$ manifold in space is the space limit at $r \rightarrow +\infty$ of the spacetime M .

$$(4.6) \quad \mathfrak{Sp}(H^\pm(S)) = \mathfrak{Sp}(\partial M)$$

But these two [4.4, 4.6] directly descend from our proof of lack of EHs, because every Σ_r hypersurface is connected to any another one by a causal curve γ (timelike ones too), given enough time any signal of matter or energy can reach any another point if its equation of motion is adapted to the path.

In a causally connected space, the time component of the Future (Past) Domain of Dependence

is determined by the time interval that null geodesics take to connect the different points $p \in M$. For this purpose we already calculated the equations of motion for light before, but the minimal time for this processes is achieved by the critical geodesic.

This is the same as the dynamical problem of Fermat's Principle, which we write as:

$$(4.7) \quad \Delta t = \int dl n(\vec{x}(l))$$

Fermat's Principle says that the optimal trajectory \vec{x} is the one by which:

$$(4.8) \quad \delta \int_A^B dl n(\vec{x}) = 0$$

Where dl is the differential optical path and n the refraction index. In our case in GR, we have the analogue condition:

$$(4.9) \quad \delta \Delta t = \delta \int_{A^\mu}^{B^\mu} dt = 0$$

Although now, we can calculate this using the geodesic equations of motion:

$$(4.10) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{dt}{dr} &= \frac{dt}{d\lambda} \frac{d\lambda}{dr} = \pm \frac{\mathcal{E} e^{-2\alpha(r)}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}} \frac{1}{\mathcal{E}} \left(e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \frac{L^2}{E^2} \frac{1}{r^2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \pm \frac{e^{-2\alpha(r)}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}} \left(e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \left(\frac{L}{E} \right)^2 \frac{1}{r^2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

As we can see the motion is independent of the energy of the photon, as we expected. Substituting [4.10] in [4.9], we can write:

$$(4.11) \quad \begin{aligned} \Delta t[\gamma] &= \int_\gamma dr \left(\frac{dt}{dr} \right) \\ \frac{\delta \Delta t[\gamma]}{\delta \gamma} &= \frac{\delta}{\delta \gamma} \int_\gamma dr \left(\frac{dt}{dr} \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Where $\gamma = \gamma(\lambda)$ is solution of the equation of motion [3.3,3.6] and $\Delta t[\gamma]$ is a functional whose domain is the space of all the solution to the null geodesic equation.

5. AFFINE NULL HYPERSURFACES

An important part of the causality problem resides in the information about null hypersurfaces, these objects specify the physical limits in information transmission between different areas on the manifold M . It can be proven that this set of manifolds are generated by geodesics. It's possible to define it as implicit manifolds by a coordinate restriction.

$$(5.1) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C} &: f(x^\mu) = 0 \\ T_x \mathfrak{C} &= \{u^\mu \in M \mid u^\mu \nabla_\mu u^\nu = 0 \wedge g_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu = 0\} \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to the null nature of these submanifolds \mathfrak{C} , we can write:

$$(5.2) \quad (T_x \mathfrak{C})^\perp = \{u_\mu \in M^* \mid u_\mu u^\mu = 0, u_\mu = \partial_\mu f\}$$

Null hypersurfaces tangent vectors are the same as their normal vectors. To work properly on these objects \mathfrak{C} we must evaluate the line element on them, which will be a restriction of the general ds^2 term for displacements in the hypersurface. This can be easily accomplished by writing the parametrization of \mathfrak{C} .

$$(5.3) \quad \mathfrak{C} : x^\mu(y^a) \mid f(x^\mu) = 0, a = 1, 2, 3$$

Where y^a are the affine coordinate to the surface. Since we are talking about a null manifold, a smart choice for such a coordinate system is the following:

$$(5.4) \quad y^a = (\lambda, \xi^2, \xi^3) \quad \text{where} \quad \begin{cases} u^\mu = \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \lambda} \\ g_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \lambda} \right) \left(\frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \xi^A} \right) = 0 \end{cases}$$

In this way the coordinate system is orthogonal and it has a dedicated coordinate λ that changes with the geodesic generator, the other two coordinates ξ^B $B = 2, 3$ represent the two-dimensional variation between the generators. We can now evaluate the metric line element by change of coordinate.

$$(5.5) \quad \begin{aligned} ds_{\mathfrak{C}}^2 &= g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu = g_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial y^a} dy^a \right) \left(\frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial y^b} dy^b \right) \\ &= h_{ab} dy^a dy^b \\ h_{ab} &= g_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial y^a} \right) \left(\frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial y^b} \right) \end{aligned}$$

By definition of our coordinate system, the induced metric has the properties:

$$(5.6) \quad \begin{aligned} h_{11} &= g_{\mu\nu} (u^\mu) (u^\nu) = 0 \\ h_{1B} &= g_{\mu\nu} (u^\mu) \left(\frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \xi^B} \right) = 0 = h_{B1} \end{aligned}$$

Equations [5.6] tell us that the manifold generated by the family of null geodesics is intrinsically two-dimensional.

$$(5.7) \quad ds_{\mathfrak{C}}^2 = h_{AB} d\xi^A d\xi^B$$

We wish to determine a orthogonal base (ξ^2, ξ^3) for the tangent space of \mathfrak{C} . The first think we should note is that the partial derivative of $x^\mu(y^a)$ with respect to λ is equal to the velocity of the generators that constitute \mathfrak{C} .

$$(5.8) \quad \frac{\partial x^\mu(y^a)}{\partial \lambda} = u^\mu(y^a)$$

From the general equations of motion [3.3, 3.6], we see that only the three parameters (E, L, L_z) can distinguish between the different solutions, this information should be inherited by the curves $x^\mu = \int d\lambda u^\mu$ themselves with the addition of the initial condition event $x^\mu(\lambda_0)$. But from our previous analysis from eq. [5.4] to [5.7], it's clear that the generator's velocities u^μ of the manifold can be told apart only by two parameters (ξ^2, ξ^3) . This apparent problem is easily solved by looking at equation [4.10] and in general remembering that the observable motion of the particle of light can't depend on its energy (if we assume that its curvature contribution is negligible). In this way, only powers of $\frac{L}{E}, \frac{L_z}{E}$ can contribute to the actual spacetime curve, from this knowledge we can redefine the affine parameter.

$$(5.9) \quad \begin{aligned} &\lambda \rightarrow \frac{\lambda}{E} \\ &\begin{cases} \dot{t} = e^{-2\alpha(r)} \\ \dot{\theta}^2 = \frac{L^2}{E^2} \frac{1}{r^4} - \frac{L_z^2}{E^2} \frac{1}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)} \\ \dot{\phi} = \frac{L_z}{E} \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \\ \dot{r}^2 = \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r} \right] \left(e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \left(\frac{L^2}{E^2} \right) \frac{1}{r^2} \right) \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Remembering that $u^\mu = (\dot{t}, \dot{r}, \dot{\theta}, \dot{\phi})^T$, we can clearly see that the new set of tangent vectors is solely dependent on $(\frac{L}{E}, \frac{L_z}{E})$. We can now chose them for our orthogonal ξ^B base. To evaluate h_{ab}

then, $\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \xi^A}$ is needed.

$$(5.10) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^A} x^\mu &= \left(\frac{\partial u^\nu}{\partial \xi^A} \frac{\partial}{\partial u^\nu} \right) x^\mu = \left(\frac{\partial u^\nu}{\partial \xi^A} \right) \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial u^\nu} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial u^\nu}{\partial \xi^A} \right) \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \lambda} \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial u^\nu} = \left(\frac{\partial u^\nu}{\partial \xi^A} \right) u^\mu (a^\nu)^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

An important consequence of our choice $\xi^B = (\frac{L^2}{E^2}, \frac{L_z}{E})$ resides in the fact that $\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \xi^B}$ are spacelike because of $\frac{\partial x^0}{\partial \xi^B} = 0$ from eqs. [5.9]. From the orthogonal relation [5.6], we get:

$$(5.11) \quad g_{ij} u^i \left(\frac{\partial u^\rho}{\partial \xi^B} \right) u^j (a^\rho)^{-1} = 0$$

We next determine the induced metric coefficients h_{AB} .

$$(5.12) \quad \begin{aligned} h_{AB} &= g_{ij} \left(\frac{\partial x^i}{\partial \xi^A} \right) \left(\frac{\partial x^j}{\partial \xi^B} \right) \\ &= g_{ij} \left(\frac{\partial u^\rho}{\partial \xi^A} \right) u^i (a^\rho)^{-1} \left(\frac{\partial u^\sigma}{\partial \xi^B} \right) u^j (a^\sigma)^{-1} = \begin{cases} \|\vec{u}\|_M I_A I_B \\ I_A = \frac{\partial u^\rho}{\partial \xi^A} \frac{1}{a^\rho} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Focusing on I_B :

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 &= \frac{\partial u^\rho}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{1}{a^\rho} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2\dot{r}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2} \dot{r}^2 \\ \frac{1}{2\dot{\theta}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2} \dot{\theta}^2 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \left(\frac{1}{a^t}, \frac{1}{a^r}, \frac{1}{a^\theta}, \frac{1}{a^\phi} \right) \\ I_3 &= \frac{\partial u^\rho}{\partial \xi^3} \frac{1}{a^\rho} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2\dot{\theta}} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3} \dot{\theta}^2 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3} \dot{\phi} \end{pmatrix} \left(\frac{1}{a^t}, \frac{1}{a^r}, \frac{1}{a^\theta}, \frac{1}{a^\phi} \right) \end{aligned}$$

With $\dot{\theta}, \dot{r} \neq 0$.

$$(5.13) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2} \dot{r}^2 &= -\frac{1}{r^2} \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r} \right], \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2} \dot{\theta}^2 = \frac{1}{r^4} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3} \dot{\theta}^2 &= -2\xi^3 \frac{1}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3} \dot{\phi} = \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \end{aligned}$$

$$(5.14) \quad \begin{aligned} I_2 &= -\frac{1}{a^r} \frac{1}{2\dot{r}r^2} \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r} \right] + \frac{1}{a^\theta} \frac{1}{2\dot{\theta}} \frac{1}{r^4} \\ I_3 &= -\frac{1}{a^\theta} \frac{1}{\dot{\theta}} \frac{1}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)} + \frac{1}{a^\phi} \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \\ a^r &= \frac{du^r}{d\lambda} = \frac{dr}{d\lambda} \frac{du^r}{dr} = (-1)^n \dot{r} \left(\left[1 - \frac{2m}{r} \right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{m}{r^2} - \frac{m'}{r} \right) \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^2}} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left[1 - \frac{2m}{r} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(e^{-2\alpha} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^2} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{\xi^2}{r^3} - \alpha' e^{-2\alpha} \right) \right) \\ a^\theta &= \dot{r} \frac{du^\theta}{dr} = (-1)^m \dot{r} \left(\frac{\xi^2}{r^4} - \frac{(\xi^3)^2}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{(\xi^3)^2}{r^5 \sin^2(\theta)} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^5} \right) \\ a^\phi &= \dot{r} \frac{du^\phi}{dr} = -\frac{2\dot{r}\xi^3}{r^3 \sin^2(\theta)} \end{aligned}$$

With $m' = \frac{dm(r)}{dr}$, $\text{sgn}(\dot{r}) = (-1)^n$, $n = 0, 1$ and $\text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}) = (-1)^m$, $m = 0, 1$.

6. MULTI-IMAGING

The observation of a light signal from a certain location resides in the fact that the two points, observer A^μ and emitter B^μ , should be located in the same generator $x^\mu \in \mathfrak{C}$, it is obvious that once the observer event $A^\mu \in \mathfrak{C}$, then there is at least one geodetic null curve passing through it from the definition of \mathfrak{C} . To define multi-imaging we can say that if there isn't a unique solution to the following equation, then there is more than one generator connecting the two events.

$$(6.1) \quad x^\mu : B^\mu = A^\mu + \int_{\lambda_A}^{\lambda_B} d\lambda \left(\frac{dx^\mu}{d\lambda} \right)$$

Another way of expressing it is that the events A^μ, B^μ can be reached without tracing any distance in the \mathfrak{C} manifold, that's because of the fact that they should be connected via generators and they evolve solely through λ .

$$(6.2) \quad ds_{\mathfrak{C}}^2 = 0 \implies h_{AB} d\xi^A d\xi^B = 0$$

In this way, the number of possible coordinates affiliated to A^μ and B^μ simultaneously in \mathfrak{C} projected to the (ξ^2, ξ^3) space is the number of solutions of eq. [6.1].

$$(6.3) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \xi_A^2 \\ \xi_A^3 \\ \xi_A^3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_B^2 \\ \xi_B^3 \\ \xi_B^3 \end{pmatrix}$$

7. CLOSED FLUXES

An interesting class of objects to consider is the Closed Fluxes \mathfrak{F}_o , which we define as:

$$(7.1) \quad \mathfrak{F}_o : x^\mu \in \mathfrak{C} \mid \pi(x^\mu) = \overline{\pi(x^\mu)}$$

$$\pi(x^\mu) = \begin{pmatrix} \xi^2 \\ \xi^3 \end{pmatrix}$$

Where $\pi(x^\mu)$ is the projection $(\lambda, \xi^2, \xi^3) \rightarrow (\xi^2, \xi^3)$ which represents a set of constant values for a flux of generators along λ . The main characteristic of this class is found when calculating the flow section, the area of a closed subset A in (ξ^2, ξ^3) space.

$$(7.2) \quad \alpha_x = \int_A d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \sqrt{h_x} \quad h_x = |\det(h_{AB}(x, \xi))|$$

Being A the spacelike section of \mathfrak{F}_o . Consider a family of generators $x_j^\mu \in \mathfrak{C}, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, then A would be the set of points in the ξ^B space that constitute a common constant of motion of the x_j^μ family.

$$(7.3) \quad A = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} \xi^2 \\ \xi^3 \end{pmatrix} \in \pi(\mathfrak{C}) \mid \partial A = \bigcup_{j=1}^n \begin{pmatrix} \xi_j^2 \\ \xi_j^3 \end{pmatrix} \wedge A = \overline{A} \right\}$$

A consequence of this is that $\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^B} h|_A = 0$, since A is a constant for x_j^μ . We can then derive the variation of the non-euclidean area α_x through spacetime by only knowing the initial condition at x_0^μ and the amplification $h(x, \xi) = \beta(x)h(\xi)$.

$$(7.4) \quad \frac{\alpha_x}{\alpha_{x_0}} = \frac{\int_A d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \sqrt{h_x}}{\int_A d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \sqrt{h_{x_0}}} = \frac{\int_A d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \beta(x) \sqrt{h_{x_0}}}{\int_A d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \sqrt{h_{x_0}}} = \beta(x)$$

We then consider the relation between the measure element of our M spacetime with its restricted counterpart in \mathfrak{C} .

$$(7.5) \quad \begin{aligned} \det(h_{AB}) &= \det \left(g_{ij} \left(\frac{\partial x^i}{\partial \xi^A} \right) \left(\frac{\partial x^j}{\partial \xi^B} \right) \right) \\ &= \det(g_{ij} J_{AB}^{ij}) = \det(g_{ij}) \det(J_{AB}^{ij}) = \det(g_{ij}) \det(J) \end{aligned}$$

Assuming the non-singular behaviour of the Jacobian matrix, then we can say that if the volume element $\sqrt{-g}$ of the family x_j^μ tends to zero, h will analogously follow. Another way of expressing it is that the convergence in a single space point of a family of geodesics implies that the α_x area tends to zero. In fact, $h|_A(x)$ represents the "concentration" of generators bundling \mathfrak{C} as a function of x^μ , with high turnout and thinning areas.

It's useful to single out the points $\mathfrak{s} : x^\mu \in \mathfrak{C} \mid h(x) = 0$, since they are the degeneracy part of \mathfrak{C} . In the particular case of a fixed orbital plane $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$, we can derive the arc element of the \mathfrak{C} manifold. From this fixing condition on the θ coordinate, we have the following ($L = L_z$):

$$\begin{cases} \dot{t} = e^{-2\alpha(r)} \\ \dot{\phi} = \frac{L_z}{E} \frac{1}{r^2} \\ \dot{r}^2 = \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r} \right] \left(e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \left(\frac{L_z^2}{E^2} \right) \frac{1}{r^2} \right) \end{cases} \quad \wedge \quad \xi^2 = (\xi^3)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} ds_{\mathfrak{C}|_{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}}}^2 &= h_{22} d\xi^2 d\xi^2 + h_{23} d\xi^2 d\xi^3 + h_{32} d\xi^3 d\xi^2 + h_{33} d\xi^3 d\xi^3 = \\ &= 4h_{22} (\xi^3)^2 (d\xi^3)^2 + 2(h_{23} + h_{32}) \xi^3 (d\xi^3)^2 + h_{33} (d\xi^3)^2 = \\ &= [4h_{22} (\xi^3)^2 + 2(h_{23} + h_{32}) \xi^3 + h_{33}] (d\xi^3)^2 \end{aligned}$$

Following the same argument as before, the set of points $\mathfrak{s}_{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}}$ is obtained from the vanishing of the arc measure element.

$$(7.6) \quad \mathfrak{s}_{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}} : [4h_{22} (\xi^3)^2 + 2(h_{23} + h_{32}) \xi^3 + h_{33}] = 0$$

This is also the condition for a curve $y^\mu \in \mathfrak{C}|_{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}}$ parametrized in ξ^3 that crossed zero distance in this restricted submanifold.

Then the constant of motion of the flux restrained in the orbital plane is the one-dimensional closed segment limited by the union of parameters ξ_j^3 of the family.

$$(7.7) \quad A_{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}} = \left\{ \xi^3 \in \pi(\mathfrak{C}_{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}}) \mid \min_j(\xi_j^3) \leq \xi^3 \leq \max_j(\xi_j^3) \right\}$$

The fixed plane situation is often used to describe point-like emission and observation of light. Consider two geodesics with ξ_1^3, ξ_2^3 the distance between them in the $\pi(\mathfrak{C}_{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}})$ changes in the x^μ space.

$$(7.8) \quad \begin{aligned} \ell_x &= \int_A ds = \int_{\xi_1^3}^{\xi_2^3} d\xi^3 f(x, \xi^3) \\ &= \int_{\xi_1^3}^{\xi_2^3} d\xi^3 [4h_{22} (\xi^3)^2 + 2(h_{23} + h_{32}) \xi^3 + h_{33}]^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

In points where the geodesics intersect they give rise to $\ell_x = 0$, this implies $\xi_2^3 = \xi_1^3$. For source and observer locations x^μ, y^μ respectively we have the simultaneous conditions:

$$(7.9) \quad \begin{cases} \ell_x = 0 \\ \ell_y = 0 \end{cases}$$

In total two independent equations and two free parameters ξ_1^3, ξ_2^3 for one final solution to the system.

The evolution of the area α_x can be analogously used to study the convergence of a family of light rays arranged in two dimensions.

7.1. Flux Energy. Treating the symmetries of the theory and their implication on the passage of light we can investigate the effects of Noether currents on close based flux tubes. In the SSS spacetime there exist a time isometry Killing vector $T^\mu = (1, 0, 0, 0)^T$ which can be used to craft a current $J^\mu = T_\nu T^{\mu\nu}$ using the energy-momentum tensor $T^{\mu\nu}$. This current is conserved through the continuity equation.

$$(7.10) \quad \nabla_\mu J^\mu = 0$$

This tells us that the (4)-volume integral of the current's divergence in a closed subset \mathcal{V} of M is equal to zero whatever the choice of \mathcal{V} . Now, from Gauss's theorem in curved spacetime:

$$(7.11) \quad \int_{\mathcal{V}} d^4x \sqrt{|g|} (\nabla_\mu J^\mu) = - \int_{\partial\mathcal{V}} d^3y \sqrt{|h|} n_\mu J^\mu$$

With the normal vector n^μ positive directed into the future and $\partial\mathcal{V}$ the boundary of the manifold \mathcal{V} . Since our current J^μ is timelike, it has zero net flux through timelike hypersurfaces, focusing on the null ones, we get:

$$(7.12) \quad \Phi_\Sigma(J) = - \int_\Sigma d^3y \sqrt{|h|} n_\mu J^\mu = - \int_\Sigma d^3y 0 \cdot n_\mu J^\mu = 0$$

Since the three-metric induced on Σ is degenerate as we have shown in section 5. It is obvious now that the notion of a conserved timelike current implies the conservation of its flux against spacelike Cauchy hypersurfaces.

$$(7.13) \quad Q_J = - \int_\Sigma d^3y \sqrt{h} n_\mu J^\mu$$

We call this quantity the conserved charge Q_J of the Noether current J^μ . Since \mathfrak{C} is defined as a null hypersurface, then the charge associated to it should be indentially zero. This doesn't tell us characterizing informations about \mathfrak{C} or any subset closed flux \mathfrak{F}_o . Although there is a natural alternative way of defining a total energy for a null flux. Spacelike Cauchy hypersurfaces Σ are naturally chosen to be of the $t = \text{const.}$ type. Using our earlier definition of space projection \mathfrak{Sp} , we can construct a spacelike manifold from \mathfrak{C} which would represent a spacelike evolution of light in M .

$$(7.14) \quad \begin{aligned} \Sigma &= \mathfrak{Sp}(\mathfrak{C}) \\ \implies T_x \Sigma &= \{k^\mu = (0, u^i)^T, i = 1, 2, 3 \mid u^\mu(\lambda) \in \mathfrak{C}\} \end{aligned}$$

The fact that Σ is nothing but a projection of a null hypersurface on a spacelike one, should imply that the internal relations in the tangent space $T_x \Sigma$ and normal $k^\mu = (0, u^i)^T$ vectors are maintained. The same coordinate change can then be chosen to finally constitute Σ parametrically.

$$(7.15) \quad \Sigma : x^\mu(y^a), y^a = (\lambda, \xi^2, \xi^3)$$

This time, λ parametrize the space projection of null geodesics, thanks to this fact the measure element \sqrt{h} isn't degenerate anymore with $h_{\alpha\beta}$ being a well-defined three-tensor. A closed flux energy is then attributed to be the flux integral of the timelike Noether current through $\mathfrak{Sp}(A)$.

$$(7.16) \quad E = -Q_J = \int_{\mathfrak{Sp}(A)} d^3y \sqrt{h} n_\mu J^\mu$$

From our choice of a spacelike hypersurface, n^μ is along the time direction, it is proportional to the asymptotic observer's four-velocity v^μ in its inertial frame, $n_\mu = g_{\mu\nu} n^\nu = (-e^{2\alpha(r)}, 0, 0, 0) = e^{\alpha(r)} v_\mu$.

(7.17)

$$\begin{aligned}
E &= \int_{\mathfrak{Sp}(A)} d^3y \sqrt{h} n_\mu J^\mu = \int_{\mathfrak{Sp}(A)} d^3y \sqrt{h} n_\mu T_\nu T^{\mu\nu} \\
&= \int_{\mathfrak{Sp}(A)} d^3y \sqrt{h} \left(-e^{2\alpha(r)}, 0, 0, 0\right) \cdot \left(-e^{2\alpha(r)}, 0, 0, 0\right) \begin{pmatrix} e^{-2\alpha(r)} \rho & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \left(1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right) p & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{p}{r^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{p}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \end{pmatrix} = \\
&= \int_{\mathfrak{Sp}(A)} d^3y \sqrt{h} \left(e^{2\alpha(r)}, 0, 0, 0\right) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \rho \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \\
&= \int_{\mathfrak{Sp}(A)} d^3y \sqrt{h} e^{2\alpha(r)} \rho(y)
\end{aligned}$$

This new energy is defined on the contribution of density in the flux tube, which is more sensible than the standard null flux integral. It is important to note that $\rho(y)$ in Σ regards a mix of components in the perfect gas, to extrapolate the energy of the radiative component E_γ we should simply specify that $\rho(y)$ is the energy density of light. We will justify this renovated notion showing that it resembles the same properties of the singled out null-path's energy definition.

Focusing only on a single limited flux tube, we can show that this energy depends on the spacial domain in which it is inscribed $h = h(x)$, then energy is not conserved in space (which we cannot tell by the fact that J^μ is purely timelike in this coordinates). Different regions of M have different energy densities, therefore their contribution vary. The simplest way to integrate on the flux tube volume is by λ -slices remembering that λ parametrizes every generator curve.

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_{\mathfrak{Sp}(A)} d^3y \sqrt{h} f(x, \xi^2, \xi^3) = \\
(7.18) \quad &= \int_{\lambda_i}^{\lambda_f} d\lambda \left(\int_{\mathfrak{Sp}(A)_\lambda} d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \sqrt{h} f(x, \xi^2, \xi^3) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

This behaviour is emblematic of gravitational redshift in a static field, it is manifested by the change in frequency as we shall see. Consider a generic observer in its own frame of reference with v^μ four-velocity, then the frequency of radiation measured is proportional to the inner product of v^μ and the null geodesic vector u^μ . Using our original parametrization λ of equations [3.3].

$$(7.19) \quad \omega_\lambda(r) = -u^\mu v_\mu = -u^0 v_0 = e^{\alpha(r)} u^0 = E e^{-\alpha(r)}$$

Two different observers at a distance of r_1 and r_2 from the center of the perfect gas distribution should experience a relative redshift dependent on r on the same light ray.

$$(7.20) \quad z_2 = \frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2} - 1 = \frac{E e^{-\alpha(r_1)}}{E e^{-\alpha(r_2)}} - 1 = \frac{e^{\alpha(r_2)}}{e^{\alpha(r_1)}} - 1$$

It is indeed independent of the light proper energy per unit mass, as well as its motion. From this derivation it's easy to show that the energy of a flux tube preserves this spherical symmetry. Consider a flux tube extending between two timelike hypersurfaces of constant radius r_i, r_f . Let

Θ be the base of the tube in (ξ^2, ξ^3) coordinates, recalling that $\rho = \rho(r)$ is solely function of r .

$$\begin{aligned}
 E &= \int_{\Sigma} d\lambda d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \sqrt{h} e^{2\alpha(r)} \rho(y) = \int_{\Sigma} dr \frac{d\lambda}{dr} d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \sqrt{h} e^{2\alpha(r)} \rho(r) = \\
 (7.21) \quad &= \int_{r_i}^{r_f} dr e^{2\alpha(r)} \rho(r) \int_{\Theta} d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \frac{\sqrt{h}}{k^1(r, \xi^2)} = \\
 &= \int_{r_i}^{r_f} dr H(r) e^{2\alpha(r)} \rho(r)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $H(r)$ is the integral in the ξ^B chunk of spacetime of $\frac{1}{k^1(r, \xi^2)}$.

$$(7.22) \quad H(r) = \int_{\Theta} d\xi^2 d\xi^3 \frac{\sqrt{h}}{k^1(r, \xi^2)}$$

This quantity is preserved for the same family of geodesics that describes Θ when calculated on the same space coordinates. Finally, the dependence of h on θ doesn't violate the spherical symmetry since $\theta = \theta(\xi^2, \xi^3, r)$ is the shape of the spacial projection of the light geodesic and it's completely determined by the choice of generator (ξ^2, ξ^3) and radius. The E of closed flux between two spheres of spacetime is the energy of a photon gas enclosed in this structure. If we suppose that the conditions of LTE (local thermodynamical equilibrium) then the spectrum is the black body radiation with a local temperature $T(r)$ which should be isotropic with respect to the perfect gas. The equality can be expressed through the Stefan-Boltzmann law $\rho = \sigma T^4$, considering only the radiative contribution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (7.23) \quad E_{\gamma} &= \int_{\Sigma} d^3x \sqrt{\gamma} \sigma T^4 = \sigma \int_{r_i}^{r_f} dr \int_{\Omega} d\theta d\phi \sqrt{\gamma} T^4(r) = \\
 &= \sigma \int_{r_i}^{r_f} dr T^4(r) \int_{\Omega} d\theta d\phi \sqrt{\gamma}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $\sqrt{\gamma}$ is the volume element of the metric induced on Σ in spacetime, since Σ is a spacelike hypersurface orthogonal to $n^{\mu} = (1, 0, 0, 0)^T$, then γ_{ij} should be:

$$(7.24) \quad \gamma_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} \left(1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right)^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^2 \sin^2(\theta) \end{pmatrix}$$

Then, $\sqrt{\gamma} = \frac{r^2 \sin(\theta)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (7.25) \quad E_{\gamma} &= \sigma \int_{r_i}^{r_f} dr T^4(r) \int_{\Omega} d\theta d\phi \sqrt{\gamma} = \sigma \int_{r_i}^{r_f} dr T^4(r) \int_{\Omega} d\theta d\phi \frac{r^2 \sin(\theta)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}} = \\
 &= \sigma \int_{r_i}^{r_f} dr \frac{r^2 T^4(r)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}} \int_{\Omega} d\theta d\phi \sin(\theta) = \sigma \int_{r_i}^{r_f} dr \frac{r^2 T^4(r) \Omega(r)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $\Omega(r) = \int_{\Omega} d\theta d\phi \sin(\theta)$ is the solid angle as a function of r along the tube. We finally found the explicit energy radial gradient:

$$(7.26) \quad \frac{dE_{\gamma}}{dr} = \sigma T^4(r) \frac{r^2 \Omega(r)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}}$$

Since in both equations [7.21] and [7.25] we are integrating in the same radial regime, we can compare the functions being integrated.

$$\begin{aligned}
(7.27) \quad & \sigma \frac{r^2 T^4(r) \Omega(r)}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}} = H(r) e^{2\alpha(r)} \rho(r) \\
& \implies T(r) = \left(\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}} \frac{H(r) e^{2\alpha(r)} \rho(r)}{\sigma r^2 \Omega(r)} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}}
\end{aligned}$$

We must now select the radiative component of the gas energy in eq. [7.21] considering the contribution to ρ . Then, $\rho(r) = \sigma T^4(r)$ and from eq. [7.27]:

$$(7.28) \quad \sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}} \frac{H(r) e^{2\alpha(r)}}{r^2 \Omega(r)} = 1 \implies H(r) = \frac{e^{-2\alpha(r)} r^2}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}} \Omega(r)$$

The explained method provides a useful and easier way to compute the $H(r)$ term which is the spacetime integral on the ξ^B space of the inverse of the radial geodetic velocity for light. To understand this identity, it is insightful to bring everything in the low curvature regime.

$$(7.29) \quad \sqrt{\gamma} \rightarrow r^2 \sin(\theta), \quad \alpha(r) \rightarrow 0 \implies H(r) \cong r^2 \Omega(r)$$

Which is the projected area of the solid angle onto the sphere of radius r .

8. COSMOLOGICAL JUNCTION

An interesting framework incorporates the exterior FLRW solution to the Einstein's equations to an interior SSS spacetime. We can thus study the light passage of cosmological origin through both spacetimes thanks to their formal junction provided by the Isreal-Darmois conditions. Let us first describe FLRW's metric and its null hypersurfaces, as it was conducted in the first part of this work. Then, we will have to regularize them at the border with the internal solutions.

$$(8.1) \quad ds^2 = -dt^2 + a^2(t) \left(\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right)$$

With k the curvature parameter and (t, r, θ, ϕ) the comoving coordinates. For solutions ($k = 1, -1$) it's clear that the argument used in section 4 to prove the causal connection of space can't be reproduced here, since this spacetime is not asymptotic Minkowskian, there is also a time asymmetry (for $k = 0$ too). From Friedmann's models for the flat and open cases, it's clear that in general such a spacetime should contain a Cosmological Horizon $R_H(t)$ at every time t . This property proves that they cannot be globally causally connected; the closed case is more interesting from this point of view, but we will not treat it here. Following the procedure of null geodesics calculation as before, it will prove useful to use Killing fields [3.2]. The FLRW Cauchy spacelike hypersurfaces have to be Maximally Symmetric in 3 dimensions by our construction choices. The standard Cosmological Principle describes the universe as isotropic and homogenous, the only three possible maximally symmetric topologies of three-dimensional space are the flat \mathbb{R}^3 , the hyperspherical \mathbb{S}^3 and lastly the hyperbolic \mathbb{H}^3 . In such a space there exist $\frac{n(n+1)}{2}$ linearly independent Killing vector fields (6 in total), three of which are rotational and the others depend on the curvature k . These three additional fields are traslationary for \mathbb{R}^3 and special

boosts for the others $k \neq 0$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{K}_1^\mu &= \sin(\phi)\partial_\theta + \frac{\cos(\phi)}{\tan(\theta)}\partial_\phi \\
\mathcal{K}_2^\mu &= \cos(\phi)\partial_\theta - \frac{\sin(\phi)}{\tan(\theta)}\partial_\phi \\
\mathcal{K}_3^\mu &= \partial_\phi \\
(8.2) \quad \mathcal{K}_4^\mu &= \chi \left(\sin(\theta)\cos(\phi)\partial_r - \frac{1}{r}\frac{\sin(\phi)}{\sin(\theta)}\partial_\phi + \frac{1}{r}\cos(\theta)\cos(\phi)\partial_\theta \right) \\
\mathcal{K}_5^\mu &= \chi \left(\sin(\theta)\sin(\phi)\partial_r + \frac{1}{r}\frac{\cos(\phi)}{\sin(\theta)}\partial_\phi + \frac{1}{r}\cos(\theta)\sin(\phi)\partial_\theta \right) \\
\mathcal{K}_6^\mu &= \chi \left(-\cos(\theta)\partial_r + \frac{1}{r}\sin(\theta)\partial_\theta \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Where we introduced $\chi = \sqrt{1 - kr^2}$.

In concomitance with the equations of motion of \mathfrak{C} in the SSS metric, we are going to use the first rotational fields ($\mathcal{K}_1^\mu, \mathcal{K}_2^\mu, \mathcal{K}_3^\mu$) to construct the following expressions for $\dot{\theta}, \dot{\phi}$.

$$(8.3) \quad \begin{cases} \dot{\theta}^2 = \frac{L^2}{r^4} - \frac{L_z^2}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)} \\ \dot{\phi} = \frac{L_z}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \end{cases}$$

Having a boost/traslational symmetry along the \hat{r} axis, we can choose \mathcal{K}_6^μ to gain an expression for radial velocity.

$$\begin{aligned}
(8.4) \quad C_6 &= u^\mu \mathcal{K}_{6\mu} = u^\mu g_{\mu\nu} \mathcal{K}_6^\nu = u^\mu \left(0, -\frac{a^2}{\chi} \cos(\theta), a^2 \chi r \sin(\theta), 0 \right) = -u^r \frac{a^2}{\chi} \cos(\theta) + u^\theta a^2 \chi r \sin(\theta) \\
&\implies \dot{r} = \chi^2 \dot{\theta} \tan(\theta) r - C_6 \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta)
\end{aligned}$$

Finally, to fix \dot{t} we can again use the fact that u^μ is null.

$$\begin{aligned}
(8.5) \quad u^\mu u_\mu &= g_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu = 0 \\
&\implies g_{tt} \dot{t}^2 + g_{rr} \dot{r}^2 + g_{\theta\theta} \dot{\theta}^2 + g_{\phi\phi} \dot{\phi}^2 = 0, g_{tt} = -1 \\
\dot{t}^2 &= \frac{a^2}{\chi^2} \dot{r}^2 + a^2 r^2 \dot{\theta}^2 + a^2 r^2 \sin^2(\theta) \dot{\phi}^2 = \frac{a^2}{\chi^2} \left(\chi^2 \dot{\theta} \tan(\theta) r - C_6 \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta) \right)^2 + a^2 r^2 \dot{\theta}^2 + a^2 \frac{L_z^2}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} = \\
&= \frac{a^2}{\chi^2} \left(\chi^4 \dot{\theta}^2 \tan^2(\theta) r^2 + C_6^2 \frac{\chi^2}{a^4} \sec^2(\theta) - 2\chi^3 C_6 \frac{\dot{\theta}}{a^2} \sin(\theta) \sec^2(\theta) \right) + a^2 r^2 \dot{\theta}^2 + a^2 \frac{L_z^2}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} = \\
&= r^2 a^2 \dot{\theta}^2 (\chi^2 \tan^2(\theta) + 1) + \frac{C_6^2}{a^2} \sec^2(\theta) - 2\chi C_6 \dot{\theta} \sin(\theta) \sec^2(\theta) + a^2 \frac{L_z^2}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)}
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the dependence of u^μ on the space of constants of motion is $u^\mu|_{\mathfrak{S}_0} = u^\mu(C_6, L^2, L_z)$, three like in the O-V case. Knowing that \mathfrak{C} should be metrically dependent on two transverse fields that describe the two-dimensional non-degenerate manifold inbetween the generators x^μ , we should be able to select two coordinates (σ^2, σ^3) instead of the standard (C_6, L^2, L_z) . We can now exploit the spherical symmetry of the FLRW spacetime to explore the motion dependence on these constants. Restraining the motion to a single orbital plane $\theta = 0$, we can differentiate between the single null

paths using (C_6, L_z) that should translate to a single σ^3 coordinate in our framework.

$$(8.6) \quad \begin{aligned} \dot{r} &= -C_6 \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta), & \dot{t}^2 &= \frac{C_6^2}{a^2} \sec^2(\theta) + a^2 \frac{L_z^2}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \\ \implies \frac{dt}{dr} &= \frac{dt}{d\lambda} \frac{d\lambda}{dr} = \mp \left(C_6^2 \frac{\chi^2}{a^4} \sec^2(\theta) \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{C_6^2}{a^2} \sec^2(\theta) + a^2 \frac{L_z^2}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \mp \left(\frac{a^2}{\chi^2} + \frac{a^6}{\chi^2} \left(\frac{L_z}{C_6} \right)^2 \cot^2(\theta) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

It is then clear that $\sigma^3 = \frac{L_z}{C_6}$, without loss of generality we can use $(\sigma^2, \sigma^3) = \left(\frac{L_z^2}{C_6^2}, \frac{L_z}{C_6} \right)$. The physical significance of the constant C_6 is found when comparing this choice of σ^B with ξ^B and by studying eq. [8.4], its absolute value seems to be proportional to the energy of the particle. The new set of equations of motion manifestly dependent on σ^B is found by redefining $\lambda \rightarrow \frac{\lambda}{C_6}$.

$$(8.7) \quad \begin{aligned} \dot{t}^2 &= a^2 \chi^2 \tan(\theta) \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{r^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \right) + a^2 \frac{\sigma^2}{r^2} + \frac{\sec^2(\theta)}{a^2} - 2\chi(-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{r^4} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)}} \sin(\theta) \sec^2(\theta) \\ \dot{r} &= \chi^2 (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{r^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)}} \tan(\theta) - \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta) \\ \dot{\theta}^2 &= \frac{\sigma^2}{r^4} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)} \\ \dot{\phi} &= \frac{\sigma^3}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \end{aligned}$$

With $m = 0, 1$ the verse of motion $\text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}) = (-1)^m$.

Now that we reproduced \mathfrak{C} in the FLRW metric, we can check if our reinvented notion of energy for null flux tubes \mathfrak{F}_\circ is compatible with what we know of the null path's energy in this spacetime. The most important phenomenon of this metric derives from the time asymmetry it implies, since there is no timelike Killing vector, Noether's theorem can't insure energy conservation in the orbits. Consider two observers with four-vectors v_1^μ, v_2^μ immersed in a flat spacetime and a light ray with four-vector tangent to its path u^μ . Since u^μ is null, its spacial component must be equal in norm to its time component. In $k = 0$ the norm of u^i is always equal to the normalized projection along a spacial traslatory Killing field \mathcal{R}^μ , in fact we can always consider a single light path as radial if the equations of motion are followed. Furthermore $v_i^\mu, i = 1, 2$ is locally a pure timelike vector.

$$(8.8) \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{\mathcal{R}_1^\mu}{\sqrt{\mathcal{R}_1^\nu \mathcal{R}_{1\nu}}} u_\mu &= -v_1^\mu u_\mu = \omega_1 \\ \frac{\mathcal{R}_2^\mu}{\sqrt{\mathcal{R}_2^\nu \mathcal{R}_{2\nu}}} u_\mu &= -v_2^\mu u_\mu = \omega_2 \end{aligned}$$

From the Killing identities, we also know $\mathcal{R}^\mu u_\mu = C$ is constant.

$$(8.9) \quad \frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2} = \frac{\sqrt{\mathcal{R}_2^\nu \mathcal{R}_{2\nu}}}{\sqrt{\mathcal{R}_1^\nu \mathcal{R}_{1\nu}}}$$

Without loss of generality (again from the SS) the norm of \mathcal{R}^μ is equal to the norm of $\mathcal{X}^\mu = (\partial_x)^\mu$ which is $\mathcal{X}^\mu \mathcal{X}_\mu = a^2(t)$.

$$(8.10) \quad \frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2} = \frac{a(t_2)}{a(t_1)}$$

The derivation was based on the flat spacetime but this behaviour of the frequency change or redshift as function of time is characteristic of every curvature choice $(\mathbb{R}^3, \mathbb{S}^3, \mathbb{H}^3)$. It's possible to

obtain the same result from our \mathfrak{C} in FLRW by choosing a single orbital plane for our null curve and posing $L_z = 0$, from eq. [8.6]:

$$(8.11) \quad \dot{t} = \pm \frac{C_6}{a(t)} \sec(\theta)$$

And in the inertial frame of reference of the two observers, remembering $v^\mu v_\mu = -1$:

$$(8.12) \quad \omega_i = -u^\mu v_\mu = -u^0 v_0 = u^0 = \dot{t}(x_i)$$

Evaluated in the spacelike position of the i -th observer. Finally our earlier result is found calculating the $\frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2}$ ratio. Returning now to our concept of eq. [7.17], we can estimate the energy of the closed flux $\mathfrak{C}\mathfrak{p}(A) = \mathcal{A}$.

$$(8.13) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C} : x^\mu &= x^\mu(y^a), \quad y^a = (\lambda, \sigma^2, \sigma^3) \\ E_{\mathcal{A}} &= \int_{\mathcal{A}} d^3y \sqrt{h} n_\mu J^\mu = \int_{\mathcal{A}} d^3y \sqrt{h} n_\mu T_\nu T^{\mu\nu} = \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{A}} d^3y \sqrt{h} (-1, 0, 0, 0) \cdot (-1, 0, 0, 0) \begin{pmatrix} \rho & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{p}{a^2}(1 - kr^2) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{p}{a^2 r^2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{p}{a^2 r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \end{pmatrix} = \\ &= \int_{\mathcal{A}} d^3y \sqrt{h} (-1, 0, 0, 0) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\rho \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \int_{\mathcal{A}} d^3y \sqrt{h} \rho(t) = \rho(t) \int_{\mathcal{A}} d^3y \sqrt{h} \end{aligned}$$

The last equality stems from the fact that $\mathcal{A} \subset \Sigma$ where Σ is a Cauchy spacelike hypersurface. We can call the three-dimensional integral over \mathcal{A} the flux-space volume $V_{\mathcal{A}}$. The dependence on $a(t)$ of $E_{\mathcal{A}}$ is then:

$$(8.14) \quad E_{\mathcal{A}} = \rho(t) V_{\mathcal{A}} \propto \rho(t) a^3(t) = \frac{\rho_0 a_0^4}{a^4(t)} a^3(t) \propto \frac{1}{a(t)}$$

Where we used the adiabatic relation for a photon gas $\rho(t) a^4(t) = \rho_0 a_0^4$. This result is completely in accordance with eq. [8.10].

8.1. Junction Conditions. With the purpose of expressing the coordinates in different spacetimes clearly, we shall write the FLRW metric with this form here:

$$(8.15) \quad ds^2 = -d\tau^2 + a^2(\tau) \left(\frac{dR^2}{1 - kR^2} + R^2 d\Omega^2 \right)$$

While maintaining the former names of the variables for the O-V metric.

To apply the Israel-Darmois conditions, we must first identify a sensible boundary in the midst of the SSS and FLRW spacetimes. The natural choice to make is a timelike spherical hypersurfaces with radius $R = R_*$, this exemplifies the symmetric nature of both the metrics and the fact that the physical distance from the center of the SSS gas distribution determines in which spacetime we are in. The $\Pi : R = R_*$ hypersurface partitions our spacetime M in two regions \mathcal{V}^- (O-V) and \mathcal{V}^+ (FLRW), to understand if they are joined smoothly at the boundary Π we must ask if the union of the two metrics $g_{\mu\nu}^+, g_{\mu\nu}^-$ provide a well defined distributional solution to the E.F.E.. We also assume that the normal vector $n^\mu = (\partial_R)^\mu = (\partial_r)^\mu$ to Π is the same from both sides $[n^\mu] = n^\mu(\mathcal{V}^+)|_\Pi - n^\mu(\mathcal{V}^-)|_\Pi = 0$ and the same is true for the Jacobian matrix between spacetime x^μ and y^a the coordinates on the tangent space of Π , so $[e_a^\mu] = \left[\frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial y^a} \right] = 0$.

In this framework, the first Israel-Darmois condition is:

$$(8.16) \quad [q_{ab}] = 0$$

With q_{ab} the metric associated with Π .

Equation [8.16] allows us to write a well defined distributional global metric as follows:

$$(8.17) \quad g_{\mu\nu} = \Theta(\ell)g_{\mu\nu}^+ + \Theta(-\ell)g_{\mu\nu}^-$$

Where $\Theta(x)$ is the Heavyside distribution and ℓ is the proper distance along the radial spacelike geodesic so that $\ell = 0$ at the passage through Π , subsequently $\text{sgn}(\ell) = \text{sgn}(\mathcal{V}^\pm)$. To ensure that [8.16] is met, we must first evaluate the metric q_{ab} on both sides of Π , starting in the \mathcal{V}^+ spacetime: Since Π is defined as the hypersurface with \mathcal{V}^+ radius R_* , then there is no radial variation.

$$(8.18) \quad \begin{aligned} dR = 0 &\implies ds_{\Pi}^2 = -d\tau^2 + a^2(\tau)R^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2(\theta)d\phi^2) \\ q_{ab} &= \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & a^2(\tau)R^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & a^2(\tau)R^2 \sin^2(\theta) \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

In the \mathcal{V}^- spacetime, we must first find the proper radius r from the comoving R , the cosmological relationship with the scale factor is thus $a(\tau)R = a_0r$.

$$(8.19) \quad \begin{aligned} R = a_0 \frac{r}{a(\tau)} &\implies dR = a_0 \frac{\partial r}{\partial \tau} \frac{dr}{a(\tau)} + a_0 r \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \left(\frac{1}{a(\tau)} \right) d\tau = \frac{a_0}{a(\tau)} dr - a_0 r \frac{\dot{a}(\tau)}{a^2(\tau)} d\tau \\ dR = 0 &\implies dr = r \frac{\dot{a}(\tau)}{a(\tau)} d\tau \end{aligned}$$

The induced metric is thus found:

$$(8.20) \quad \begin{aligned} ds_{\Pi}^2 &= -e^{2\alpha(r(\tau))}t'^2 d\tau^2 + e^{2\beta(r(\tau))}R^2 \frac{\dot{a}^2}{a_0^2} d\tau^2 + \frac{a^2(\tau)}{a_0^2} R^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2(\theta)d\phi^2) = \\ &= -d\tau^2 \left(e^{2\alpha(r(\tau))}t'^2 - e^{2\beta(r(\tau))} \frac{\dot{a}^2}{a_0^2} R^2 \right) + \frac{a^2(\tau)}{a_0^2} R^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2(\theta)d\phi^2) \\ q_{ab} &= \begin{pmatrix} - \left(e^{2\alpha(r(\tau))}t'^2 - e^{2\beta(r(\tau))} \frac{\dot{a}^2}{a_0^2} R^2 \right) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a^2(\tau)}{a_0^2} R^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{a^2(\tau)}{a_0^2} R^2 \sin^2(\theta) \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Where $t' = \frac{dt}{d\tau}$. On the boundary Π , we should have the metric equivalence.

$$(8.21) \quad \begin{cases} e^{2\alpha(r(\tau))}t'^2 - e^{2\beta(r(\tau))} \frac{\dot{a}^2}{a_0^2} R^2 = 1 \\ a_0 = 1 \end{cases}$$

Which constitutes the final equation:

$$(8.22) \quad t'^2 = e^{-2\alpha(r(\tau))} \left(1 + e^{2\beta(r(\tau))} \dot{a}^2 R^2 \right)$$

From eq. [8.22] it is now possible to integrate for $t(\tau)$ with this the motion of the boundary shell Π is completely solved in both spacetimes \mathcal{V}^\pm .

$$(8.23) \quad \begin{cases} R_* = \text{const.} \\ r_*(t) = a(t)R_* \\ t(\tau) : e^{2\alpha(r(\tau))}t'^2 - e^{2\beta(r(\tau))} \dot{a}^2 R^2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

We can now proceed to the second Israel-Darmois condition:

$$(8.24) \quad [K_{ab}] = 0$$

With K_{ab} the extrinsic curvature tensor of the Π manifold, we also have the definitions:

$$(8.25) \quad \begin{aligned} [K_{ab}] &= - \left[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\gamma} \right] n_{\gamma} e_a^{\alpha} e_b^{\beta} \\ S_{ab} &= - \frac{\varepsilon}{8\pi} ([K_{ab}] - [K] q_{ab}) \end{aligned}$$

Here, S_{ab} is the surface energy-momentum tensor and $\varepsilon = n^{\mu} n_{\mu}$ the norm of the normal vector. From this last expression we can write the global energy-momentum tensor on M .

$$(8.26) \quad T_{\mu\nu} = \Theta(\ell) T_{\mu\nu}^+ + \Theta(-\ell) T_{\mu\nu}^- + \delta(\ell) S_{\mu\nu}$$

Where $S^{\mu\nu} = S^{ab} e_a^{\mu} e_b^{\nu}$ is the composition from Π . It's possible to show that if condition [8.24] is not met, then $T_{\mu\nu}$ is singular on the passage through Π ($S_{ab} \neq 0$). We wish to evaluate this discontinuity on the passage of light u^{μ} . A brief calculation reveals that the singular contribution to the Christoffel symbol is attributed to $\left[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} \right]$:

$$(8.27) \quad \partial_{\delta} \Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} = \Theta(\ell) \partial_{\delta} \Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{+\alpha} + \Theta(-\ell) \partial_{\delta} \Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{-\alpha} + \varepsilon \delta(\ell) \left[\Gamma_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} \right] n_{\delta}$$

This difference in the Christoffel symbol on the boundary constitutes an impulsive acceleration on the geodesic:

$$(8.28) \quad a_{\Pi}^{\mu} := \left[\frac{d^2 x^{\mu}}{d\lambda^2} \right] = -\delta(\lambda_{\Pi}) \left[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} \right] \frac{dx^{\alpha}}{d\lambda} \frac{dx^{\beta}}{d\lambda}$$

Where λ_{Π} indicates the affine parameter value at which the geodesic passes through the boundary between \mathcal{V}^+ and \mathcal{V}^- . We can evaluate the difference in velocity Δu^{μ} integrating a_{Π}^{μ} .

$$(8.29) \quad \Delta u^{\mu} = \int d\lambda a_{\Pi}^{\mu} = - \int d\lambda \delta(\lambda_{\Pi}) \left[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} \right] u^{\alpha} u^{\beta} = - \left[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} \right] u^{\alpha} u^{\beta} \Big|_{\lambda_{\Pi}=0}$$

We can evaluate the external velocity starting from the value of the internal one, Δu^{μ} is defined as the contribution from $\mathcal{V}^- \rightarrow \mathcal{V}^+$.

$$(8.30) \quad u^{+\mu} = u^{-\mu} - \left[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} \right] (u^{-\alpha} u^{-\beta}) \Big|_{\lambda_{\Pi}=0}$$

The only independent non-null Christoffel symbols in the O-V metric are:

$$(8.31) \quad \begin{aligned} \Gamma_{01}^0 &= \partial_r \alpha & \Gamma_{00}^1 &= e^{2(\alpha-\beta)} \partial_r \alpha & \Gamma_{11}^1 &= \partial_r \beta \\ \Gamma_{12}^2 &= \frac{1}{r} & \Gamma_{22}^1 &= -r e^{-2\beta} & \Gamma_{13}^3 &= \frac{1}{r} \\ \Gamma_{33}^1 &= -r e^{-2\beta} \sin^2(\theta) & \Gamma_{33}^2 &= -\sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) & \Gamma_{23}^3 &= \frac{\cos(\theta)}{\sin(\theta)} \end{aligned}$$

And for FLRW:

$$(8.32) \quad \begin{aligned} \Gamma_{11}^0 &= \frac{a\dot{a}}{1-kR^2} & \Gamma_{11}^1 &= \frac{kR}{1-kR^2} & \Gamma_{22}^0 &= a\dot{a}R^2 \\ \Gamma_{33}^0 &= a\dot{a}R^2 \sin^2(\theta) & \Gamma_{01}^1 &= \Gamma_{02}^2 = \Gamma_{03}^3 = \frac{\dot{a}}{a} \\ \Gamma_{22}^1 &= -R(1-kR^2) & \Gamma_{33}^1 &= -R(1-kR^2) \sin^2(\theta) & \Gamma_{12}^2 &= \Gamma_{13}^3 = \frac{1}{R} \\ \Gamma_{33}^2 &= -\sin(\theta) \cos(\theta) & \Gamma_{23}^3 &= \cot(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

The difference $\Delta\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} = \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{+\mu} - \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{-\mu}$ is then:

$$\begin{aligned}
(8.33) \quad \Delta\Gamma_{11}^0 &= \frac{a\dot{a}}{1-kR^2} & \Delta\Gamma_{11}^1 &= \frac{kR}{1-kR^2} - \partial_r\beta & \Delta\Gamma_{22}^0 &= a\dot{a}R^2 \\
\Delta\Gamma_{33}^0 &= a\dot{a}R^2 \sin^2(\theta) & \Delta\Gamma_{01}^1 &= \Delta\Gamma_{02}^2 = \Delta\Gamma_{03}^3 = \frac{\dot{a}}{a} \\
\Delta\Gamma_{22}^1 &= -R(1-kR^2) + re^{-2\beta} & \Delta\Gamma_{33}^1 &= -R(1-kR^2) \sin^2(\theta) + re^{-2\beta} \sin^2(\theta) \\
\Delta\Gamma_{12}^2 &= \Delta\Gamma_{13}^3 = \frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{r} & \Delta\Gamma_{33}^2 &= \Delta\Gamma_{23}^3 = 0 \\
\Delta\Gamma_{01}^0 &= -\partial_r\alpha & \Delta\Gamma_{00}^1 &= -e^{2(\alpha-\beta)}\partial_r\alpha
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(8.34) \quad \Delta u^0 &= -[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^0] u^\alpha u^\beta = -\frac{a\dot{a}}{1-kR^2} \dot{r}^2 - a\dot{a}R^2 \dot{\theta}^2 - a\dot{a}R^2 \sin^2(\theta) \dot{\phi}^2 + 2\partial_r\alpha \dot{r} \\
\Delta u^1 &= -[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^1] u^\alpha u^\beta = \left(-\frac{kR}{1-kR^2} + \partial_r\beta\right) \dot{r}^2 - 2\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \dot{r} \dot{\theta} + \\
&+ (R(1-kR^2) - re^{-2\beta}) \dot{\theta}^2 + (R(1-kR^2) \sin^2(\theta) - re^{-2\beta} \sin^2(\theta)) \dot{\phi}^2 + e^{2(\alpha-\beta)} \partial_r\alpha \dot{r}^2 \\
\Delta u^2 &= -[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^2] u^\alpha u^\beta = -2\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \dot{r} \dot{\theta} - 2\left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{r}\right) \dot{r} \dot{\phi} \\
\Delta u^3 &= -[\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^3] u^\alpha u^\beta = -2\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \dot{r} \dot{\phi} - 2\left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{r}\right) \dot{r} \dot{\phi}
\end{aligned}$$

Applying the equations of motion in the SSS spacetime for \mathfrak{C} : [5.9].

$$\begin{aligned}
(8.35) \quad \Delta u^0 &= -\frac{a\dot{a}}{1-kR^2} \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right] \left(e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^2}\right) - a\dot{a}R^2 \frac{\xi^2}{r^4} + \\
&+ 2(-1)^n \partial_r\alpha e^{-2\alpha(r)} \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^2}} \\
\Delta u^1 &= \left(-\frac{kR}{1-kR^2} + \partial_r\beta\right) \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right] \left(e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^2}\right) + \\
&- 2(-1)^n \frac{\dot{a}}{a} e^{-2\alpha(r)} \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^2}} + (R(1-kR^2) - re^{-2\beta}) \frac{\xi^2}{r^4} + e^{-2(\alpha+\beta)} \partial_r\alpha \\
\Delta u^2 &= (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\xi^2}{r^4} - \frac{(\xi^3)^2}{r^4 \sin^2(\theta)}} \left(-2\frac{\dot{a}}{a} e^{-2\alpha(r)} - 2(-1)^n \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{r}\right) \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^2}}\right) \\
\Delta u^3 &= \frac{\xi^3}{r^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \left(-2\frac{\dot{a}}{a} e^{-2\alpha(r)} - 2(-1)^n \left(\frac{1}{R} - \frac{1}{r}\right) \left[1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha(r)} - \frac{\xi^2}{r^2}}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

With $n = 0, 1$ if the photon is directed outwards or inwards respectively and $m = 0, 1$ determines the verse of the rotation $\text{sgn}(\dot{\theta}) = (-1)^m$. Imposing the conditions of affinity to the hypersurface

II: [8.23].

(8.36)

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta u^0 &= -\frac{a\dot{a}}{1-kR_*^2} \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right] \left(e^{-2\alpha} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}\right) - \dot{a} \frac{\xi^2}{a^3 R_*^2} + 2(-1)^n \alpha' e^{-2\alpha} \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}} \\
\Delta u^1 &= \left(-\frac{kR_*}{1-kR_*^2} + \beta'\right) \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right] \left(e^{-2\alpha} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}\right) + \\
&\quad -2(-1)^n \frac{\dot{a}}{a} e^{-2\alpha} \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}} + (1-kR_*^2 - ae^{-2\beta}) \frac{\xi^2}{a^4 R_*^3} + e^{-2(\alpha+\beta)} \alpha' \\
\Delta u^2 &= (-1)^m \frac{1}{a^2 R_*^2} \sqrt{\xi^2 - \frac{(\xi^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta)}} \left(-2\frac{\dot{a}}{a} e^{-2\alpha} - 2\frac{(-1)^n}{R_*} \left(1 - \frac{1}{a}\right) \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}}\right) \\
\Delta u^3 &= \frac{\xi^3}{a^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \left(-2\frac{\dot{a}}{a} e^{-2\alpha} - 2\frac{(-1)^n}{R_*} \left(1 - \frac{1}{a}\right) \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

For notational efficiency we suppressed the function arguments and shortened the differentiation with respect to r : $\partial_r \alpha = \alpha'$, $\partial_r \beta = \beta'$. The radial null geodesic subset of \mathfrak{C} would constitute the following discontinuity values:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta u^0 &= -\frac{a\dot{a}}{1-kR_*^2} \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right] e^{-2\alpha} + 2(-1)^n \alpha' \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{-3\alpha} \\
(8.37) \quad \Delta u^1 &= \left(-\frac{kR_*}{1-kR_*^2} + \beta'\right) \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right] e^{-2\alpha} - 2(-1)^n \frac{\dot{a}}{a} \left[1 - \frac{2m}{aR_*}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{-3\alpha} + e^{-2(\alpha+\beta)} \alpha' \\
\Delta u^2 &= \Delta u^3 = 0
\end{aligned}$$

8.2. Consequences.

8.2.1. Perturbed Path Redshift. These quantities represent the gravitational refraction at the thin shell, this behaviour is typical of the situations in which there is an energy-mass distribution on a hypersurface with zero (4)-volume. It constitutes a discontinuity in the velocity u^μ of light with an instantaneous change in direction (the spacial component) and energy (time component). It also has consequences on the observed redshift when compared to the case of a pure FLRW light travel, these differences designate a way of determining the magnitude of the perturbation on the null path. We can first study the simplest case: radial passage of light throughout the SSS bubble to understand the difference with respect to the unperturbed case. In this case since there is only a family of geodesics that could intersect both the source and the observer, the only important quantity to evaluate is the energy of the light signal or equivalently the time taken $\Delta\tau$. The first part of the motion is in the FLRW spacetime, going from the observer to the margin of the SSS bubble.

$$(8.38) \quad \Delta\tau_1 = \int_{\tau_s}^{\tau_i} d\tau = \int_{a(\tau_s)}^{a(\tau_i)} \frac{da}{\dot{a}}$$

The second part is through the SSS spacetime, from equation [4.10].

$$(8.39) \quad \Delta t = t_f - t_i = \int_0^{r_*(t_i)} dr \frac{e^{-3\alpha(r)}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}} + \int_0^{r_*(t_f)} dr \frac{e^{-3\alpha(r)}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2m(r)}{r}}}$$

And the final part equal in form to the first one:

$$(8.40) \quad \Delta\tau_2 = \int_{\tau_f}^{\tau_o} d\tau = \int_{a(\tau_f)}^{a(\tau_o)} \frac{da}{\dot{a}}$$

In general we can say that this total time interval of the perturbed path $\Delta\tau_p = \Delta\tau_1 + \Delta t(\tau) + \Delta\tau_2$ differs from the unperturbed count $\Delta\tau = \int_{a(\tau_s)}^{a(\tau_o)} \frac{da}{a}$. We will now show that the argument from which we based our analysis of the (ξ^2, ξ^3) and (σ^2, σ^3) coordinate systems is no longer globally valid. The passage of light through another spacetime \mathcal{V}^- solution to E.F.E. changes the constants of motion living in the external space time \mathcal{V}^+ . Consider the frequency relation with the free parameter [8.11]:

$$(8.41) \quad \omega(\tau) = \frac{d\tau}{d\lambda} = \frac{C_1}{a(\tau)} \quad C_1 \text{ constant}$$

Since energy is conserved inside SSS the only contribution to its passage are the impulsive boundary terms $\Delta u_i^0, \Delta u_f^0$ for the entrance and release respectively.

$$(8.42) \quad \omega(\tau_f) = \omega(\tau_i) - \Delta u_i^0 + \Delta u_f^0$$

Now the new outgoing particle must behave like the standard cosmological relation $\omega \propto \frac{1}{a(\tau)}$.

$$(8.43) \quad \omega(\tau) = \frac{C_2}{a(\tau)} \quad C_2 \text{ constant}$$

Putting all together we get the relation between the constants of motion:

$$(8.44) \quad \frac{C_2}{a(\tau_f)} = \omega(\tau_i) - \Delta u_i^0 + \Delta u_f^0 = \frac{C_1}{a(\tau_i)} - \Delta u_i^0 + \Delta u_f^0 \implies C_2 = a(\tau_f) \left(\frac{C_1}{a(\tau_i)} - \Delta u_i^0 + \Delta u_f^0 \right)$$

Notice that even in the case of a continuous passage through II, the constants would change $C_2 = C_1 \frac{a(\tau_f)}{a(\tau_i)}$. This is a result of the fact that while the light passes through the energy-conserving \mathcal{V}^- spacetime, the exterior \mathcal{V}^+ keep changing through τ and when the perturbed particle returns to \mathcal{V}^+ it should be intrinsically different from the unperturbed ones. Calculating the redshift for the radial case:

$$(8.45) \quad z = \frac{\omega_s}{\omega_o} - 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{cases} \omega_s = \frac{C_1}{a(\tau_s)} \\ \omega_o = \frac{C_2}{a(\tau_o)} \end{cases}$$

$$z = \frac{C_1 a(\tau_o)}{C_2 a(\tau_s)} - 1 = \frac{C_1}{a(\tau_f)} \left(\frac{C_1}{a(\tau_i)} - \Delta u_i^0 + \Delta u_f^0 \right)^{-1} \frac{a(\tau_o)}{a(\tau_s)} - 1$$

If we again consider the passage as continuous:

$$(8.46) \quad z_c = \frac{a(\tau_i) a(\tau_o)}{a(\tau_f) a(\tau_s)} - 1$$

Under the assumption that the physical path x^μ cannot depend on the frequency of light, we should weigh the additional terms $\Delta u_i^0, \Delta u_f^0$ with C_1 which is equivalent to using the original set of eqs. of motion [3.3,3.6] in eqs. [8.37]. We can now show the result for the non-radial case, analogously as before from eqs. [8.7]:

$$(8.47) \quad \omega(\tau, R, \theta) = C_6 \left(a^2 \chi^2 \tan(\theta) \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{R^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R^2 \sin^2(\theta)} \right) + a^2 \frac{\sigma^2}{R^2} + \frac{\sec^2(\theta)}{a^2} + \right. \\ \left. - 2\chi(-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R^4} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R^4 \sin^2(\theta)}} \sin(\theta) \sec^2(\theta) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

At the release of the boundary, in accordance with eq. [8.42]:

$$(8.48) \quad \omega(\tau_f, R_*, \theta_f) = \omega(\tau_i, R_*, \theta_i) - \Delta u_i^0 + \Delta u_f^0$$

(8.49)

$$\begin{aligned}
& C'_6 \left(a^2 \chi^2 \tan(\theta_f) \left(\frac{\sigma_f^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma_f^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta_f)} \right) + a^2 \frac{\sigma_f^2}{R_*^2} + \frac{\sec^2(\theta_f)}{a^2} + \right. \\
& - 2\chi(-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_f^2}{R_*^4} - \frac{(\sigma_f^3)^2}{R_*^4 \sin^2(\theta_f)}} \sin(\theta_f) \sec^2(\theta_f) \left. \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = C_6 \left(a^2 \chi^2 \tan(\theta_i) \left(\frac{\sigma_i^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma_i^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta_i)} \right) + a^2 \frac{\sigma_i^2}{R_*^2} + \frac{\sec^2(\theta_i)}{a^2} + \right. \\
& \left. - 2\chi(-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_i^2}{R_*^4} - \frac{(\sigma_i^3)^2}{R_*^4 \sin^2(\theta_i)}} \sin(\theta_i) \sec^2(\theta_i) \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \Delta u_i^0 + \Delta u_f^0
\end{aligned}$$

By first principles it is possible to determine C'_6 as function of $C_6, \sigma_i^2, \sigma_i^3$ from the fact that (σ_f^2, σ_f^3) derives from the starting constants (σ_i^2, σ_i^3) before the entrance of the light ray in the SSS bubble. To do this it is necessary to study the relation between internal and external constants of motion. Finally the altered redshift is obtain by the familiar equation:

$$(8.50) \quad z = \frac{\omega_s(C_6, \sigma_i^2, \sigma_i^3)}{\omega_0(C'_6, \sigma_f^2, \sigma_f^3)} - 1$$

8.2.2. *Relationship between \mathcal{V}^+ and \mathcal{V}^- constants of motion spaces $(\sigma^2, \sigma^3) \longleftrightarrow (\xi^2, \xi^3)$.* Generalizing what we described to be the case for the radial passage of light and time component u^0 of the null geodesic, we can derive the relation between σ^B and ξ^B variables describing \mathfrak{C} in $\mathcal{V}^+, \mathcal{V}^-$ respectively. From the fact that even if there is a instantaneous contribution Δu^μ on the parametric curve, it still constitutes a geodesic, we can renormalize the entire set of equations of motion to new constants of motion, schematically: $(\xi^2, \xi^3) + \Delta u^\mu \rightarrow (\tilde{\xi}^2, \tilde{\xi}^3)$. It is appropriate to evaluate ξ^B as functions of σ^B since the Π boundary is much more natural in FLRW coordinates.

$$(8.51) \quad \begin{aligned} & \dot{\phi}(\mathcal{V}^+)|_\Pi - \dot{\phi}(\mathcal{V}^-)|_\Pi = \Delta u^3 \\ & \frac{\sigma^3}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)} - \frac{\xi^3}{a^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)} = \Delta u^3 \implies \frac{\xi^3}{a^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)} = \frac{\sigma^3}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)} - \Delta u^3 \\ & \rightarrow \xi^3 = a^2 \sigma^3 - \Delta u^3 a^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

(8.52)

$$\begin{aligned}
& \dot{\theta}(\mathcal{V}^+)|_\Pi - \dot{\theta}(\mathcal{V}^-)|_\Pi = \Delta u^2 \\
& \frac{1}{R_*^2} \sqrt{\sigma^2 - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta)}} - \frac{1}{a^2 R_*^2} \sqrt{\xi^2 - \frac{(\xi^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta)}} = \Delta u^2 \implies \sqrt{\xi^2 - \frac{(\xi^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta)}} = a^2 \sqrt{\sigma^2 - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta)}} - a^2 R_*^2 \Delta u^2 \\
& = \frac{(\xi^3(\sigma^3))^2}{\sin^2(\theta)} + \left(a^2 \sqrt{\sigma^2 - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta)}} - a^2 R_*^2 \Delta u^2 \right)^2 = \\
& \rightarrow \xi^2 = \left(\frac{a^2 \sigma^3 - \Delta u^3 a^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}{\sin(\theta)} \right)^2 + \left(a^2 \sqrt{\sigma^2 - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta)}} - a^2 R_*^2 \Delta u^2 \right)^2
\end{aligned}$$

Notice that ξ^2 which is the constant of motion associated to the total angular momentum per energy per mass is both dependent on σ^2 and σ^3 , accordingly the internal $L_{\mathcal{V}^-}^2$ relates to the external $L_{\mathcal{V}^+}^2$ and $L_{\mathcal{V}^+ z}$ values. This couple of equations [8.51, 8.52] delineate the constant of motion spaces in $\mathcal{V}^+, \mathcal{V}^-$, and as a consequence also \mathfrak{F}_0 . This tells us how the light bundles change configuration passing through different spacetimes. However, there are two additional conditions to respect, they

are expressed by the differences $\dot{\tau}(\mathcal{V}^+)|_{\Pi} - \dot{\tau}(\mathcal{V}^-)|_{\Pi}$ and $\dot{R}(\mathcal{V}^+)|_{\Pi} - \dot{r}(\mathcal{V}^-)|_{\Pi}$.

$$(8.53) \quad \begin{aligned} \dot{\tau}(\mathcal{V}^+)|_{\Pi} - \dot{\tau}(\mathcal{V}^-)|_{\Pi} &= \Delta u^0 \\ \dot{\tau}(\mathcal{V}^+)|_{\Pi} &= \Delta u^0 + e^{-2\alpha(r_*(\tau))} \implies \dot{\tau}^2|_{\Pi} = \left(\Delta u^0 + e^{-2\alpha(\tau)}\right)^2 \\ \left(\Delta u^0 + e^{-2\alpha(\tau)}\right)^2 &= a^2 \chi^2 \tan(\theta) \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}\right) + a^2 \frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} + \frac{\sec^2(\theta)}{a^2} + \\ &\quad - 2 \frac{\chi}{R_*} (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}} \sin(\theta) \sec^2(\theta) \end{aligned}$$

We can try solving it for the $x = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}}$ term since eq. [8.53] is a quadratic for x .

$$(8.54) \quad \begin{aligned} \left(\Delta u^0 + e^{-2\alpha(\tau)}\right)^2 &= Ax^2 - Bx + C \\ Ax^2 - Bx + C' &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Where $A = a^2 \chi^2 \tan(\theta)$, $B = 2 \frac{\chi}{R_*} (-1)^m \sin(\theta) \sec^2(\theta)$, $C = a^2 \frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} + \frac{\sec^2(\theta)}{a^2}$, $C' = C - (\Delta u^0 + e^{-2\alpha(\tau)})^2$. Using the quadratic formula we get:

$$(8.55) \quad \begin{aligned} x_{1,2} &= \frac{B \pm \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC'}}{2A} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}} \\ \frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)} &= \left(\frac{B \pm \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC'}}{2A}\right)^2 \implies (\sigma^3)^2 = \sigma^2 \sin^2(\theta) - R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta) \left(\frac{B \pm \sqrt{B^2 - 4AC'}}{2A}\right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

Applying the definitions mentioned above, we finally get the resulting equation:

$$(8.56) \quad \begin{aligned} \rightarrow (\sigma^3)^2 &= \sigma^2 \sin^2(\theta) - \frac{R_*^2 \cos^2(\theta)}{4a^4 \chi^4} \left(2 \frac{\chi}{R_*} (-1)^m \sin(\theta) \sec^2(\theta) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \pm \sqrt{4 \frac{\chi^2}{R_*^2} \sin^2(\theta) \sec^4(\theta) - 4a^2 \chi^2 \tan(\theta) \left(a^2 \frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} + \frac{\sec^2(\theta)}{a^2} - (\Delta u^0 + e^{-2\alpha(\tau)})^2\right)}\right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

Which is a relationship solely relating on $(\sigma^3)^2 = f(\sigma^2)$. Based on what said for the previous result, we draw from this that $L_{\mathcal{V}^+}$ is a function of $L_{\mathcal{V}^-}$, τ , R_* , θ .

$$(8.57) \quad \begin{aligned} \dot{R}_*(\mathcal{V}^+)|_{\Pi} - \dot{r}(\mathcal{V}^-)|_{\Pi} &= \Delta u^1 \\ \chi^2 (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}} \tan(\theta) - \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta) - (-1)^n \left[1 - \frac{2m(r_*)}{aR_*}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha(r_*)} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}} &= \Delta u^1 \\ (-1)^n \left[1 - \frac{2m(\tau)}{aR_*}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha(\tau)} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}} &= \chi^2 (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}} \tan(\theta) - \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta) - \Delta u^1 \\ \implies \sqrt{e^{-2\alpha(\tau)} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2}} &= (-1)^{-n} \left[1 - \frac{2m(\tau)}{aR_*}\right]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \left(\chi^2 (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}} \tan(\theta) - \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta) - \Delta u^1\right) \\ e^{-2\alpha(\tau)} - \frac{\xi^2}{a^2 R_*^2} &= \left[1 - \frac{2m(\tau)}{aR_*}\right]^{-1} \left(\chi^2 (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}} \tan(\theta) - \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta) - \Delta u^1\right)^2 \\ \rightarrow \xi^2 &= a^2 R_*^2 e^{-2\alpha(\tau)} - a^2 R_*^2 \left[1 - \frac{2m(\tau)}{aR_*}\right]^{-1} \left(\chi^2 (-1)^m \sqrt{\frac{\sigma^2}{R_*^2} - \frac{(\sigma^3)^2}{R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta)}} \tan(\theta) - \frac{\chi}{a^2} \sec(\theta) - \Delta u^1\right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

This last equation can be seen as an alternative to eq. [8.52] and implies other conditions on σ^B . From eqs. [8.51,8.52] we are able to extrapolate the relations between old and new σ^B coordinates of the generators after a passage in \mathcal{V}^- . Since in the internal spacetime (ξ^2, ξ^3) are constants, we

can draw from this:

$$(8.58) \quad \begin{aligned} \xi_i^3 = \xi_f^3 &\implies a_i^2 \sigma_i^3 - \Delta u_i^3 a_i^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta_i) = a_f^2 \sigma_f^3 - \Delta u_f^3 a_f^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta_f) \\ &\rightarrow \sigma_f^3 = \left(\frac{a_i}{a_f}\right)^2 \sigma_i^3 + R_*^2 \left(\Delta u_f^3 \sin^2(\theta_f) - \Delta u_i^3 \left(\frac{a_i}{a_f}\right)^2 \sin^2(\theta_i) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Notice that in the continuous case $\Delta u_i^3 = \Delta u_f^3 = 0$ we would have:

$$(8.59) \quad \sigma_f^3 = \left(\frac{a_i}{a_f}\right)^2 \sigma_i^3$$

While the C_6 variation was $C'_6 = \frac{a_f}{a_i} C_6$ from eq. [8.44].

(8.60)

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_i^2 = \xi_f^2 & \\ \left(\frac{a_i^2 \sigma_i^3 - \Delta u_i^3 a_i^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta_i)}{\sin(\theta_i)} \right)^2 + \left(a_i^2 \sqrt{\sigma_i^2 - \frac{(\sigma_i^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta_i)}} - a_i^2 R_*^2 \Delta u_i^2 \right)^2 &= \\ = \left(\frac{a_f^2 \sigma_f^3 - \Delta u_f^3 a_f^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta_f)}{\sin(\theta_f)} \right)^2 + \left(a_f^2 \sqrt{\sigma_f^2 - \frac{(\sigma_f^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta_f)}} - a_f^2 R_*^2 \Delta u_f^2 \right)^2 & \\ a_f^2 \sqrt{\sigma_f^2 - \frac{(\sigma_f^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta_f)}} - a_f^2 R_*^2 \Delta u_f^2 &= \\ = \pm \left(\left(\frac{a_i^2 \sigma_i^3 - \Delta u_i^3 a_i^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta_i)}{\sin(\theta_i)} \right)^2 + \left(a_i^2 \sqrt{\sigma_i^2 - \frac{(\sigma_i^3)^2}{\sin^2(\theta_i)}} - a_i^2 R_*^2 \Delta u_i^2 \right)^2 - \left(\frac{a_f^2 \sigma_f^3 - \Delta u_f^3 a_f^2 R_*^2 \sin^2(\theta_f)}{\sin(\theta_f)} \right)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

Calling the second member of the equation Q for notational simplicity:

$$(8.61) \quad \rightarrow \sigma_f^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_f^3(\sigma_i^3)}{\sin(\theta_f)} \right)^2 + \frac{(Q + a_f^2 R_*^2 \Delta u_f^2)^2}{a_f^4}$$

In the continuous case:

$$(8.62) \quad \sigma_f^2 = \left(\frac{a_i}{a_f}\right)^4 \sigma_i^2$$

In section 7 we showed how the lensing problem can be discussed in terms of convergence of two geodesics to a couple of points (source, observer). The system [7.9] can be uniquely used in \mathcal{V}^- spacetime, but we can analyze the same problem in a similar context: solve the lensing (find the coordinates $\sigma_{i,j}^3, j = 1, 2$) for two geodesics intersecting in two space points in \mathcal{V}^+ by passing throughout \mathcal{V}^- . Considering a one-dimensional closed flux base A , then the formula expressing the spacelike distance between the generators of $\mathfrak{C}|_{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}}$ is the following:

$$(8.63) \quad \ell_x = \int_{A_i} ds = \int_{\sigma_{i,1}^3}^{\sigma_{i,2}^3} d\sigma^3 [4h_{22}(\sigma_i^3)^2 + 2(h_{23} + h_{32})\sigma_i^3 + h_{33}]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

With h_{AB} the induced metric on \mathfrak{C} in \mathcal{V}^+ . If both geodesics passed in the internal spacetime, we should consider the altered distance: $\tilde{\ell}$ relating the distance in the space of coordinates altered by the passage: (σ_f^2, σ_f^3) .

$$(8.64) \quad \tilde{\ell}_x = \int_{A_f} ds = \int_{\sigma_{f,1}^3}^{\sigma_{f,2}^3} d\sigma^3 [4h_{22}(\sigma_f^3)^2 + 2(h_{23} + h_{32})\sigma_f^3 + h_{33}]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Imposing the conditions of convergence eq. [7.9], we still get a system with a unique solution since $\sigma_f^B = \sigma_f^B(\sigma_i^B)$. Lastly, we can make an important observation: we can attribute to \mathcal{V}^- the role of a

gravitational converging lens. The function that maps the σ_i^B space into σ_f^B is an endomorphism in the σ^B space and it seems to describe a contraction considering a metrical space (σ^B, d) embedded with a distance. The following scheme describes the variation of the external constant of motion space:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} & & \sigma_f(\sigma_i) & & \\ & \nearrow & \text{---} & \searrow & \\ \mathcal{V}^+ & \xrightarrow{\xi(\sigma)} & \mathcal{V}^- & \xrightarrow{\sigma(\xi)} & \mathcal{V}^+ \end{array}$$

This fact is obvious from the continuous limit (zero energy-momentum tensor on Π) eqs. [8.59,8.62] considering a monotonically expanding universe in a time interval $\Delta\tau$. In this way, the contraction driven by the internal behaviour of spacetime "pulls" different generators closer to the unique fixed-point. In this limit, the unique fixed-point is clear to be $(\sigma^2, \sigma^3) = (0, 0)$ since $a_i/a_f \leq 1$. Every \mathcal{V}^- passage tends to radial behaviour of the interested light bundle.

9. CONCLUSION

We have studied the causal structure and light handling in the primordial collapsed bubble resulted from the spherical collapsed gas in the early universe. This mathematical framework of closed-fluxes, constants of motion spaces ξ^B, σ^B and lensing/redshift effects give us an overview of this complex problem. We achieved a solution to the multi-imaging lensing problem providing eq. [7.9] and its 2-dimensional counterpart with α_x . This optimizes numerical calculations since, instead of computing the entire light path algorithmically, we can just solve two integrals numerically in the ξ^B or σ^B space and imposing the above-said conditions. We also gave an alternative definition for the closed-flux energy motivated by the resembling properties characteristic of single null geodesics both in \mathcal{V}^\pm . Finally treating the problem of the SSS bubble immersed in a FLRW context, gave us important insights in the cosmic-gravitational refraction caused by the non-zero surface energy-momentum tensor S_{ab} and modified redshift of perturbed paths. We can conclude that the presence of these symmetric structures in the early formation eras of our universe should have caused the slowdown of the standard cosmological redshift process and an overall converging effect on the radiative component of the primordial fluid. Considering the relations $\sigma^2 = L^2/C_6^2, \sigma^3 = L_z/C_6$ and a continuous passage between the matched spacetimes \mathcal{V}^\pm (z_r only takes into account the radial journey):

$$(9.1) \quad z_r = \frac{a_i a_o}{a_f a_s} - 1$$

$$(9.2) \quad L_{f,z} = \frac{a_i}{a_f} L_{i,z}, \quad L_f^2 = \left(\frac{a_i}{a_f}\right)^2 L_i^2$$

Where the subscripts i, f stand for the scale factor $a(\tau)$ evaluated before and after the passage in \mathcal{V}^- respectively, the subscript s, o stand for the evaluation at the source and observer immersed in \mathcal{V}^+ .

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